

INTRA-HEPATIC VESSEL SEGMENTATION AND CLASSIFICATION IN MULTI-PHASE CT USING OPTIMIZED GRAPH CUTS

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ABSTRACT

The segmentation and classification of the major intra-hepatic blood vessels are critical for the robust identification of the segmental anatomy of the liver. We propose a novel 4D graph-based method to segment and label the hepatic and portal veins. The algorithm uses multi-phase CT images to model the differential enhancement of the liver structures and Hessian-based vesselness likelihood to avoid the common pitfalls of graph cuts-based intra-hepatic vessel segmentation. A hybrid classification step identifies the right, middle and left hepatic, and portal veins. We tested the method on CT data from nine patients and comparatively found that the new vesselness and enhancement graph costs are effective in reducing the effects of heterogeneous noise and vessel fragmentation.

INDEX TERMS: *contrast-enhanced CT, liver, hepatic vein, portal vein, segmentation, classification, graph.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Precise patient specific knowledge of hepatic vasculature and segmental anatomy are essential elements of liver therapy and surgical planning. Contrast enhanced computed tomography (CT) is the predominant 3D imaging modality for non-invasive hepatic analysis and surgical planning due to its ability to highlight the intra-hepatic vascular network when a contrast agent is injected into the patient's blood stream. In this context, computer-aided clinical tools can facilitate optimal diagnostic and therapeutic decisions for the treatment of liver diseases.

Information about the proximity of tumors to the major branches of the hepatic and portal veins is a key determinant of a patient's suitability for surgical resection of hepatocellular carcinomas (HCC) [1]. Minimally invasive therapies for HCC, including radio frequency ablation, also require detailed knowledge of tumor location in order to accurately estimate risk and efficacy, as well as estimate convective heat loss from large blood vessels. Similarly, the advanced planning of living donor liver transplantation must ensure that the grafted liver volume is independently functional [2]. These tasks are complicated by a high degree

of variability in individual liver structure and shape [3], which makes the development of automated computer tools to identify and localize hepatic segmental anatomy and vascular networks challenging.

The Couinaud atlas is the most widely accepted classification for liver segmental anatomy [4]. The Couinaud atlas divides the liver into eight segments such that each has independent vascular circulation and biliary drainage. Liver resections or surgery are best defined by the limits of individual Couinaud segments to ideally minimize damage to the remaining segments.

Past attempts to develop automated and semi-automated computer tools for identifying the segments specified by the Couinaud atlas in 3D CT data have demonstrated varying degrees of success, but are all highly dependent on the quality of segmentation and classification of the major intra-hepatic veins [2, 5-7]. Methods used for intra-hepatic vessel segmentation include region growing, optimal thresholding, edge detection, vessel tracking, Hessian-based vesselness, and level set based methods [2, 5-9]. These techniques are sensitive to image acquisition, local variations in enhancement and branching of vessels.

Recently, graph-based image segmentation methods have gained increasing attention in biomedical image analysis as a result of their ability to find a globally optimal fast solution to segmentation problems [10]. In these applications, the input data are represented as a graph and an optimal cut based on a cost or energy function splits the nodes of the graph into two sets—the desired object and the background. In its basic form, the graph cuts algorithm is not well suited to segmenting elongated structures like vessels due to its tendency to generate a cut with minimum cost. This limitation is termed the shrinking bias problem, as the sum of costs along the elongated boundary of the vessel may be higher than the cost of making a cut through the vessel, generating an incorrect segmentation [11].

Using graph cuts, Esneault et al. developed a method for liver vessel segmentation that incorporated cylindrical geometrical moments to determine the likelihood of a voxel in the 3D CT input data being part of a vessel [12]. Kaftan et al. employed a 3D graph cuts segmentation initialized by a gradient divergence-based vessel enhancing filter, which was not incorporated in the global optimization [13]. Their

techniques were sensitive to parameter tuning and did not address the intra-hepatic vessel labeling.

Previously, we developed a graph cuts method to segment abdominal organs, including the liver, from contrast-enhanced CT data [14]. In this study, we propose a novel 4D graph-based method to segment and classify the major large diameter intra-hepatic vasculature: the hepatic and portal veins. Smaller hepatic arterial tree runs alongside the portal veins, thus is not vital to be segmented for the purpose of surgical resection. The graph cuts segmentation incorporates constraints for vasculature enhancement from 4D multi-phase CT images (non-contrast and portal venous enhancement phases) and a Hessian-based vesselness filter to provide new vessel-likelihood cost terms. Finally, the segmented vessels are classified into right, middle and left hepatic, and left and right portal veins using a hybrid process that incorporates anatomical information and competitive region growing.

2. METHODS

The liver vessels segmentation and classification method was tested on nine patient multi-phase CT data sets. The abdominal CT studies had normal liver anatomy, without major relevant vascular anomalies or variants. CT images were acquired at two temporal phases, a non-contrast phase image (NCP) and a portal venous enhancement phase (PVP) image captured at a fixed delay (GE Healthcare LightSpeed Ultra and QX/I scanners, Milwaukee, WI). The image slice thickness was 1mm and in slice resolutions ranged from 0.66 mm to 0.82 mm.

Liver masks were obtained using a previously developed graph cuts segmentation method [14]. NCP images were registered to PVP images using the non-linear registration algorithm in [15]. An example is shown in Figure 1. 4D data were smoothed using anisotropic diffusion [16].

Figure 1: Multi-phase liver CT; a) the registered NCP image; b) the PVP image; and c) the liver mask shown on PVP data [14]. The intra-hepatic veins appear dark in a) and bright in b).

The graph cuts method for image segmentation operates by finding a globally optimal cut through the graph based on the input data. The graph is constructed by assigning a node for each voxel p . In this case, the input for each patient is represented by 4D CT data including NCP and PVP images. Thus, for each voxel p , there are two associated intensity

values, I_{NCP}^p and I_{PVP}^p . Graph cuts segmentation requires a set of seed points for the object to be segmented, in this case the intra-hepatic vessels, and a set of seed points for the background in order to generate intensity probability distributions for the object and background labels. In this study, these seed points were generated automatically by finding an optimal threshold in the PVP data for each case using the method in [5]. As thresholding is sensitive to image intensity and noise, conservative vessel masks were captured, which were incomplete vessels, with attempted minimizing the inclusion of false positives.

There are two terminal nodes in the graph corresponding to the source (for object), and the sink (for background). Every node is connected to both the source and the sink via t-links. The t-link costs traditionally correspond to regional information, log-likelihoods of voxels belonging to the object or background class [10]. Similarly, n-links are placed between adjacent voxels in a connected grid. In traditional graphs, the costs assigned to n-links discourage cuts between two voxels of similar intensity.

Given a binary vector $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p\}$ where each element is associated with a voxel in the input image and each element's value is a binary label representing the object to be segmented or the background, the cost function of the graph E in our application can be written as

$$E(A) = E_{data}(A) + E_{enhance}(A) + E_{vesselness}(A) + E_{boundary}(A),$$

where the first three terms represent the cost for the t-links and $E_{boundary}$ represents the n-links.

Intensity histograms for the object (vessels) were built from the seed voxels in NCP and PVP images. A background mask was then created by inverting the object mask and eroding it. Background intensity histograms were also computed. Sums of Gaussians were fit to the histograms to generate probability distribution functions P .

E_{data} is the regional term that computes penalties based on the 4D histograms of the object and backgrounds. Thus, the term is defined as follows:

$$E_{data}(A) = \lambda \sum_{p \in O} R_p(O) + (1 - \lambda) \sum_{p \in B} R_p(B);$$

$$R_p(O) = -\ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{P_{ncp}(I_{ncp}^p | O) P_{pvp}(I_{pvp}^p | O)}}{\sqrt{P_{ncp}(I_{ncp}^p | O) P_{pvp}(I_{pvp}^p | O) + \sqrt{P_{ncp}(I_{ncp}^p | B) P_{pvp}(I_{pvp}^p | B)}}} \right)$$

$E_{enhance}$ is the regional term that penalizes voxels that do not rapidly enhance between the PVP and the NCP images. The vessels should enhance significantly more than the parenchyma as they carry the contrast agent (see Figure 1).

$$E_{enhance}(A) = \delta \sum_{p \in O} R_{pMP}(O) + (1 - \delta) \sum_{p \in B} R_{pMP}(B);$$

$$I_{MP}^p = |I_{PVP}^p - I_{NCP}^p|;$$

$$R_{pMP}(O) = -\ln \left(\frac{P_{MP}(I_{MP}^p | O)}{P_{MP}(I_{MP}^p | O) + P_{MP}(I_{MP}^p | B)} \right).$$

Hessian-based vesselness likelihoods were generated from the PVP image data using an implementation of the multi-scale curvilinear structure enhancing filter developed by Sato et al. [17]. The multiscale vesselness measure V is defined as:

$$E_{vesselness} = -\ln(V) \quad \text{with} \quad V = \max_{\sigma} \{ \sigma^2 \cdot \lambda_{123}(p, \sigma) \} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\lambda_{123} = \begin{cases} |\lambda_2| + \lambda_1, & \lambda_3 < \lambda_2 < \lambda_1 \leq 0 \\ |\lambda_2| - 0.25 \cdot \lambda_1, & \lambda_3 < \lambda_2 < 0 < \lambda_1 \leq \frac{|\lambda_2|}{0.25} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where p is a voxel in the PVP image, σ is the scale of the Gaussian convolution used to calculate the discrete Hessian, and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ are the eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix.

The n-link costs between adjacent voxels p and q are initially assigned symmetrically as

$$E_{boundary}(A) = \mu \sum_{\{p,q\} \in N_p} w_{\{p \rightarrow q\}} + (1 - \mu) \sum_{\{p,q\} \in N_p} w_{\{q \rightarrow p\}}$$

$$w_{\{p \rightarrow q\}} = w_{\{q \rightarrow p\}} = \begin{cases} 0 & , \text{if } A_p = A_q \\ \exp\left(-\frac{|I_{ncp}^p - I_{ncp}^q| \cdot |I_{pvp}^p - I_{pvp}^q|}{2\sigma_{ncp}\sigma_{pvp}}\right) \frac{1}{dist(p,q)} & , \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

However, an additional directional constraint penalizes transitions from dark to bright in the PVP image and transitions from bright to dark in the non-contrast phase, as vessels should be brighter than parenchyma in PVP and darker than parenchyma in NCP (see Figure 1).

$$\text{IF} \left((I_{pvp}^p - I_{pvp}^q) > \sigma_{pvp} \text{ OR } (I_{ncp}^q - I_{ncp}^p) > \sigma_{ncp} \right),$$

$$\text{THEN } w_{\{q \rightarrow p\}} = 1;$$

$$\text{ELSE } w_{\{p \rightarrow q\}} = 1,$$

where σ_{pvp} and σ_{NCP} are the standard deviations associated with noise in each respective phase. In our study, the parameters δ, μ and λ were balanced and set to 0.5.

The vessel classification is based on the relative anatomical locations of the major veins in the liver. To ensure that the hepatic and portal venous systems are not erroneously connected due to partial volume effects, the initial segmentation of the vasculature is morphologically opened. This is sufficient to separate the hepatic vein branches from one another as well as from the portal vein. Next, a connected component analysis is performed to find the four largest connected components, which correspond to the left hepatic, right hepatic, middle hepatic, and portal veins. The portal vein is identified as the inferior component based on the liver anatomy [4]. The remaining hepatic branches are labeled according to location in the liver.

After morphological opening, the smaller vessels appear eroded and the vasculature mask is incomplete. To obtain a finer segmentation including labeling, a competitive region growing algorithm grew each of the vein branches back into the results of the graph cuts segmentation. The region fronts were propagated at equal rates for each vein until all voxels

in the vasculature masks were labeled. Finally, the labeled veins were skeletonized using a 3-D parallel thinning algorithm [18].

3. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the segmentation and labeling of intra-hepatic veins in 2D slices of 3D CT data. The hepatic vasculature was correctly identified and classified into the major vessel trees in the liver: the portal and right, middle and left hepatic veins.

To illustrate the effects of introducing the $E_{vesselness}$ and $E_{enhance}$ terms in our 4D graph formulation, we performed comparative tests using a traditional graph cuts algorithm [10]. As seen in Figure 3, the basic graph cuts segmentation was sensitive to local variations of the contrast enhancement in the liver. As the liver is a large organ, contrast enhancement is heterogeneous and local regions that are highly enhanced tend to be labeled incorrectly as vessels by the basic graph cuts algorithm.

Figure 3 also presents segmentation results using the vesselness measure in [17] to assess the likelihood of a voxel belonging to a tubular structure. The vesselness is less sensitive to uneven contrast enhancement as long as the shape of a structure is preserved, but is affected by noise and artifacts in the data, which results in discontinuous segmentations of vessels and spurious detections. Additionally, this measure used alone can miss branching regions of the vessels where the local shape is not tubular.

Finally, Figure 3 also shows segmentation results from the optimal thresholding technique in [5]. As expected, this intensity-based method is affected by image appearance and quality, but an erosion of its results is sufficient to initialize our algorithm.

Figure 2: An example of segmentation and labeling of intra-hepatic veins on 2D axial slices of 3D CT data; the top row shows the liver in PVP with enhanced vessels; the bottom row presents the corresponding segmented images with the portal vein in blue and the right, middle and left hepatic veins in red, yellow and green, respectively.

Figure 3: 3D rendering of the intra-hepatic veins; a) from a traditional graph cuts algorithm [10]; b) using the vesselness filter in [17]; c) using our technique; d) a skeletonization of our segmentation based on [18].

Our technique combines vesselness and enhancement likelihoods in a globally optimal graph-based method and avoids the segmentation problems encountered by previous algorithms. The enhancement term incorporates the 4D nature of the input data in our method and models the difference in enhancement between liver vasculature and parenchyma. Additionally, the algorithm performs vasculature labeling, an essential step for the potential identification of liver segments.

In future work, we will develop a fully automated system to identify the liver segmental anatomy using the hepatic vasculature in normal and abnormal cases.

4. CONCLUSION

A novel graph-based method for the segmentation of the major intra-hepatic blood vessels is presented. The method avoids the shortcomings of the traditional graph cuts or intensity-based vessel segmentation methods by including 4D enhancement modeling and vesselness likelihoods. The segmented vessels were correctly classified into right, middle and left hepatic, and portal veins using a hybrid process that incorporates anatomical information and competitive region growing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by the Intramural Research Program of the National Institutes of Health, Clinical Center.

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